

Cyclic grafted polymers: Synthesis, Properties and Biomedical Applications

Carlo Andrea Pagnacco,^{a,b,c} Fabienne Barroso-Bujans^{*a,b,c,d}

^aDonostia International Physics Center (DIPC), Paseo Manuel Lardizábal 4, 20018 Donostia–San Sebastián, Spain

^bMaterials Physics Center, CSIC-UPV/EHU, Paseo Manuel Lardizábal 5, 20018 Donostia–San Sebastián, Spain

^cPMAS, Faculty of Chemistry, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Paseo Manuel Lardizábal 3, 20018 Donostia–San Sebastián, Spain

^dIKERBASQUE - Basque Foundation for Science, Plaza Euskadi 5, 48009, Bilbao, Spain

Abstract

Cyclic grafted polymers, which feature a ring-shaped backbone densely functionalized with side chains, are among the most interesting emerging architectures due to their unique three-dimensional structures and tunable properties. This review outlines synthetic methodologies for forming cyclic grafted polymers and explores the principles and implications of polymer grafting by analyzing their physical properties and self-aggregation behavior. Through a critical examination of their synthesis, structural features, and functional potential, this review emphasizes the expanding opportunities that cyclic grafted polymers offer, especially in developing advanced materials and biomedical platforms for drug delivery, gene transfection, and biomaterials engineering.

Keywords

Cyclic polymers; Ring polymers; Grafted polymers; Macroinitiators; Grafting; Branches

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Abbreviations: MW, molecular weight; DP, degree of polymerization; RC, ring closure; CuAAC, Cu-catalyzed alkyne/azide cycloaddition; REP, ring expansion polymerization; REMP, ring expansion metathesis polymerization; ROP, ring-opening polymerization; ROMBP, ring-opening multibranching polymerization; ZROP, zwitterionic ring-opening polymerization; ZREP zwitterionic ring expansion polymerization; ATRP, atom transfer radical polymerization; NMRP, nitroxide mediated-radical polymerization; AFM, atomic force microscopy; TEM, transmission electron microscopy; GPC, gel permeation chromatography; SAXS, small angle x-ray scattering; DSC, differential scanning calorimetry; LCST, lower critical solution temperature; BBB, blood-brain barrier; PLA, polylactic acid; PS, polystyrene; PnBA, poly(*n*-butyl acrylate); PCL, poly(ϵ -caprolactone); PEO, poly(ethylene oxide); PSLi, polystyryllithium; PCEVE, poly(chloroethyl vinyl ether); PAA, poly(acrylic acid); PtBA, poly(*tert*-butyl acrylate); PEG, poly(ethyleneglycol); TAD, triazolinedione; PGMA, poly(glycidyl methacrylate); POEGMA, poly(oligo(ethylene glycol) methacrylate); EGMA, ethyl glycinate methacrylamide; PTEPM, poly(3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl methacrylate); DEDA, *N,N*-

diethylethylenediamine; ATL, *N*-acryloylhomocysteine thiolactone; PEGA, poly(ethylene glycol) methyl ether acrylate; PMMA, poly(methacrylic acid); poly(*t*BMA), poly(*tert*-butyl methacrylate); PVAc, poly(vinyl acetate); pDMAEMA, poly(*N,N*-dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate); PNAM, poly(*N*-acryloylmorpholine); PMDETA, *N,N,N',N'',N'''*-pentamethyldiethylenetriamine; NBS, *N*-bromo succinimide; TFA, trifluoroacetic acid; DOX, doxorubicin; SBMA, [2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl]dimethyl-(3-sulfopropyl); cPG, cyclic polyglycidol; bcPG, branched cyclic polyglycerol; hbPG, hyperbranched polyglycerol; *t*BGE, *tert*-butyl glycidyl ether; HEMA, 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate; HEAAm, *N*-hydroxyethylacrylamide.

1. Introduction

The topology of a polymer plays a fundamental role in its physicochemical properties. Cyclic polymers, due to their ring-shaped structure, exhibit significantly different properties compared to their linear counterparts such as lower melt viscosities, higher glass transition temperatures (T_g), lower hydrodynamic volumes, reduced entanglements, and longer *in vivo* blood circulation times, making cyclic polymers interesting in biomedicine, materials engineering, and surface functionalization.¹⁻⁷ Cyclic polymers are synthesized by two main approaches: ring closure (RC) and ring expansion polymerization (REP). The RC method involves the use of a linear polymeric precursor with compatible chain-end groups, which are coupled intramolecularly using highly efficient reactions (e.g. “click”, Diels-Alder cycloaddition) or bimolecularly using a difunctional coupling agent. This strategy allows forming cyclic polymers with well-defined molecular weight (MW) and low dispersity. However, to avoid oligomerization of the linear precursor, very high dilution conditions are required, limiting the mass scale

of the cyclic product. The REP method involves the use of a cyclic monomer or a cyclic initiator. The monomer is incorporated into a cyclic structure generated by the initiation step, which propagates while maintaining the cyclic shape. Finally, the elimination of the initiator produces the cyclic polymer. REP does not require highly dilute conditions, but the mechanism suffers from less control over the MW than RC, and polymers with high dispersity are often obtained. Several reviews have detailed the synthetic methods and applications of cyclic polymers, highlighting that cyclic topology is a topic of great interest in polymer science.¹⁻¹⁶

Polymer grafting, a process that entails the covalent attachment of side chains to a polymer backbone, is a prevalent technique employed to modify the properties of polymers. This method facilitates the creation of a synergistic effect between the distinct characteristics of the backbone and the side chains, resulting in the enhancement of the overall properties of the polymer.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ For instance, the grafting of hydrophilic side chains onto a hydrophobic polymer backbone can render the polymer soluble in water and biocompatible.²⁰ Pendant chains can also increase the surface available for functionalization²¹ or encapsulation of small molecules,²² thereby creating opportunities for drug delivery.

The grafting density is defined as the number of side chains per repeating unit of the backbone. If each repeating unit carries one side chain, the grafting density is calculated as 100%. In general, high grafting densities impart conformational rigidity to the grafted polymer chain due to steric interactions between adjacent side chains. As a result, the polymer adopts chain-extended conformations and defined three-dimensional shapes such as cylinders for linear backbones and donuts for cyclic backbones.^{18, 23}

The recent increase in demand for cyclic polymers has driven research into efficient production methods with high yields and reproducibility. Today, cyclic polymers can be

synthesized from a wide range of monomers, paving the way for more complex structures such as the cyclic grafted polymers.

Cyclic grafted polymers are characterized by a cyclic backbone, wherein the repeating unit is linked to other polymeric chains that form the pendant chains. **Figure 1** illustrates the cyclic grafted structures that can be obtained, as discussed in this review. In the case of pendant chains composed of linear polymer chains, the resulting structure is commonly referred to as a cyclic brush, cyclic comb, or jellyfish polymer. In the case of pendant chains that are composed of branched chains, the resulting structure is designated as a cyclic branched polymer. Finally, when the pendant groups are constituted by well-defined generations of repeating units (G_n) that form ordered "tree-like" architectures, the resulting structure is designated as a cyclic dendronized polymer. In terms of composition, brushes can be formed by homopolymers, block copolymers, gradient copolymers and random copolymers. They can also be forming more complex structures, such as Y-junctions and multigrfts.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of different possible structures for cyclic grafted polymers.

The aim of this review is to provide an overview of the synthetic routes for the formation of cyclic grafted polymers and to offer a critical perspective on their properties, which make them interesting for a number of potential biomedical applications.

2. Synthesis of cyclic grafted polymers

For the synthesis of cyclic grafted polymers, three main strategies have been reported in the literature,^{23, 24} differentiated by the necessity or not of an *a priori* formed cyclic polymer (**Figure 2**). (I) The "grafting-through" approach, commonly known as the macromonomer approach: the cyclic backbone is formed during the polymerization of macromonomers bearing the desired pendant chains. (II) The "grafting-onto" approach: preformed polymer chains are attached to a preformed cyclic backbone in a convergent fashion through highly efficient reactions. (III) The "grafting-from" approach: pendant chains are generated in a divergent manner by polymerization steps from the cyclic backbone (macroinitiator). A fourth strategy can be added to these known strategies: (IV) The "monomer approach": a cyclic branched polymer is obtained directly during the polymerization reaction. This reaction combines cyclization and the formation of branches. Few cases have been reported due to the need for a specific catalyst and monomer pair.^{25, 26} In general, the above strategies can be used to generate homopolymers and copolymers with a wide variety of backbones and side chains (linear, branched or dendronized) as discussed in detail below.

Figure 2. The four strategies used to generate cyclic grafted polymers.

2.1. Grafting-through or macromonomer approach

The “grafting-through” strategy is often the first choice for synthesizing linear dendrons and bottlebrush polymers.^{19, 27} However, few reports have been published on the synthesis of cyclic grafted structures using this strategy. The great advantage of polymerizing a macromonomer is that polymers with 100% grafting density are assured. However, the main difficulties in the synthesis of cyclic dendronized polymers are the limited choice of macromonomers available for REP (the only reported polymerization method to date) and the steric effects resulting from the presence of side chains in the macromonomer, requiring the use of highly efficient catalysts.

In 2009, Grubbs et al.²⁸ reported the synthesis of cyclic dendronized polymers containing a second-generation polyester dendron by ring expansion metathesis polymerization (REMP) of a ω -norbornenyl macromonomer (**Figure 3a**). A degree of polymerization (DP) as high as 5000 was achieved using Ru-based metathesis catalysts SC-5 and UC-6. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements confirmed the toroidal shape of the obtained polymers with a diameter of 35 nm and a cavity of about 5 to 7 nm. In 2011, the same group reported the synthesis of cyclic brush polymers *via* REMP of ω -norbornenyl macromonomers containing polylactide (PLA), polystyrene (PS) and poly(*n*-butyl

acrylate) (*PnBA*) of different MW (**Figure 3b**).²⁹ As expected, the monomer conversion decreased by increasing the MW of the ω -norbornenyl macromonomer. This tendency was higher for SC-5 than for SC-6. Less active UC-5 and UC-6 catalysts resulted in minimal conversion. The MW obtained was extremely high, exceeding one million Da in all cases. AFM confirmed the formation of cyclic structures with diameters ranging from 100 to 180 nm, toroidal shapes and large, open pores that are larger than those reported previously.²⁸ Interestingly, ring scission of individual cyclic brush polymers was observed after they were left on a graphite surface for 2 h, a phenomenon that had previously been observed in linear brush polymers.³⁰

Figure 3. Grafting-through approach. Synthesis of cyclic poly(norbornene imide)-grafted structures by REMP of R-macromonomers containing (a) R = aryl ether dendron,²⁸ (b) R = PLA, PS and PnBA²⁹ and (c) R = PDMS and PS.³¹ The catalyst [Cat] used in each polymerization reaction is indicated.

In 2024, Golder et al.³¹ reported the synthesis of well-controlled polymerization of PS and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)-based ω -norbornenyl macromonomers using a new REMP catalyst, pyr-CB6, developed by their group (**Figure 3c**).^{32, 33} The authors observed a good molar mass control over a wide range of target DPs (DP = 10–50) while maintaining low dispersities for both polymerization systems. They also reported improved initiation efficiency compared to other Ru-based REMP catalysts (eg. SC-5)²⁹ based on the achievement of $M_n < 50$ kDa, which is well below the ultra-high MW obtained in previous studies.

In 2023, Wu and Liu et al.³⁴ reported the synthesis of cyclic poly(phenylisocyanide)-based polymers by living REP of functionalized isocyanide macromonomers. They developed a cyclic catalyst based on alkyne-Pd(II) able to insert isocyanide monomers in a living way (**Figure 4**), confirmed by the linearity between MW and $[M]_0/[Cat]_0$ while maintaining a dispersity (\bar{D}) between 1.15 and 1.20. Cyclic brush polymers were obtained using this catalyst for the REP of a macromonomer that ended in a phenyl isocyanide and was composed of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) with different DP values of 60 and 100 (**Figure 4**). The resulting cyclic brush polymers exhibited variations in diameter with the DP of the cyclic backbone and variations in wall thickness with the DP of the PLA side chain, as measured by transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Notably, the polymer formed with a cyclic backbone DP of 150 and a PLA side chain DP of 100 showed a diameter of 600 nm and a wall thickness of 50 nm.

Figure 4. Living REP of isocyanide-based macromonomers catalyzed by a cyclic alkyne-Pd(II) catalyst generating cyclic grafted structures by using the "grafting-through" approach.³⁴

2.2. Grafting-onto approach

The main characteristic of the "grafting-onto" approach is that the cyclic backbone and the pendant chains are synthesized separately, allowing the generation of well-controlled architectures. However, highly efficient coupling reactions are required to overcome the hindrance of reactive groups along the cyclic backbone, which can lead to incomplete grafting processes. For example, the synthesis of "sun-shaped" polymers with a backbone of cyclic poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) and poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) pendant chains was reported with a grafting efficiency of about 50-60%.³⁵ The cyclic backbone was first synthesized by copolymerization of ϵ -caprolactone (ϵ CL) and a monomer containing a protected hydroxyl group, γ -triethylsilyloxy- ϵ -caprolactone, followed by a cyclization reaction and deprotection of hydroxyl groups. COOH-terminated PEO chains of about 1000 Da were then grafted onto the cyclic backbone by esterification, a reaction that often does not proceed to completion.

One of the first syntheses of cyclic grafted polymers by the "grafting-onto" approach was reported by Deffieux in 1999 (**Figure 5**).³⁶ They successfully grafted polystyryllithium

(PSLi) chains onto a cyclic poly(chloroethyl vinyl ether) (PCEVE) backbone by reaction with the chloroethyl ether side groups. Using the disappearance of the red color of PSLi in dry toluene as a reaction indicator, they ensured reaction completion by the reappearance of the color upon addition of a slight excess of PSLi relative to the chloroethyl ether units. The grafting density, determined by the ratio of the M_n of the cyclic grafted polymer to that of the PS branches, was close to 100%. A similar grafting strategy was used several years later by Matsushita et al.,³⁷ where PSLi chains were grafted onto a cyclic PS copolymer backbone containing 4-(3-butenyl) styrene anchor points.

Figure 5. Synthesis of cyclic PCEVE-*g*-PS *via* grafting of PSLi chains onto a cyclic PCEVE backbone through nucleophilic substitution as described by Deffieux et al.³⁶ The cyclic PCEVE backbone was synthesized using an RC strategy.

In 2015, Zhu et al.³⁸ reported the use of the Suzuki coupling between a cyclic poly(4-bromostyrene) backbone and PS chains terminated by an arylboronic acid pinacol ester group as a means to synthesize cyclic grafted polymers (**Figure 6**). The authors reported quantitative grafting demonstrating the potential of Suzuki coupling as a highly efficient reaction for grafting side chains onto central backbones.

Figure 6. Synthesis of cyclic PS-g-PS using Suzuki coupling as described by Zhu et al.³⁸

The cyclic poly(4-bromostyrene) backbone was synthesized using an RC strategy.

"Click" chemistry is one of the most efficient and simple approaches to coupling high MW fragments to a variety of "entities".^{22, 39-41} The first breakthrough synthesis of cyclic dendrons by the "grafting-onto" route was reported by Grayson et al.⁴² They successfully grafted polyester dendrons up to the third generation (G1-G3) onto a cyclic poly(4-acetoxystyrene) backbone using the Cu-catalyzed alkyne-azide cycloaddition (CuAAC) "click" reaction (**Figure 7**), achieving 90% grafting efficiency at the third generation without loss of monomodality. The authors also reported the synthesis of analogous cyclic dendronized polymers using the divergent "grafting-from" strategy, in which iterative reactions of esterification and hydrogenolysis were performed starting from a cyclic poly(4-acetoxystyrene). Although the reaction was successful up to third generation, the loss of monomodality was observed at higher generation of dendritic growth. As explained by the authors, the "grafting-onto" approach was more effective than the "grafting-from" strategy in controlling structural properties such as polydispersity, degree of grafting, dendron generation and MW of the resulting structures.

Figure 7. Synthesis of cyclic dendronized polyesters as described by Grayson et al.⁴² The cyclic poly(4-acetoxystyrene) was synthesized using an RC strategy.

In 2022, Li et al.⁴³ reported the synthesis of a library of cyclic brush polymers composed of a cyclic poly(acrylic acid) (PAA) backbone with PS side chains (PAA-g-PS) of different ring sizes and grafting densities. They first prepared a cyclic poly(*tert*-butyl acrylate) (P*t*BA) with different MWs using the RC approach. Then, acidic hydrolysis of the *t*Bu side groups led to the formation of cyclic PAA, which upon reaction with propargyl bromide generated clickable alkyne side groups. Finally, azide-terminated PS chains (PS-N₃) were grafted onto the cyclic backbone by CuAAC click reaction. By adjusting the azide/alkyne feed ratio, various grafting densities were obtained, but without achieving 100 % grafting, probably due to the steric hindrance that typically occurs in “grafting-onto” approaches, as mentioned above.

In 2011, Tew et al.⁴⁴ grafted PEG chains onto a cyclic polynorbornene backbone containing activated pentafluorophenol ester side groups in two different ways (**Figure 8**). In route 1, the cyclic polymer backbone was reacted with an amine-terminated PEG with a MW of 550 g/mol (PEG-NH₂ 550) and in route 2, the same cyclic polymer backbone was reacted first with propargylamine and then with an azide-terminated PEG

with an identical MW of 550 g/mol (PEG-N₃ 550) using the CuAAC click reaction. The author reported extremely high grafting efficiencies (>95%) for both methods, demonstrating that amidation of highly activated pentafluorophenol esters is as efficient as CuAAC for grafting low MW PEG side chains. AFM measurements confirmed the circular shape of the resulting cyclic grafted polymers with an outer diameter of approximately 30 nm. By relying on the reaction of amines with the activated pentafluorophenol ester side groups, Tew et al.⁴⁵ incorporated quantitative amounts of terpyridine ligands onto a cyclic polynorbornene structure, which are known for their ability to chelate transition metal ions. Subsequently, by reacting the PEG-terpyridine-Ru(III) monocomplex with the terpyridine side chains of the cyclic polymer backbone, a metallo-supramolecular cyclic brush polymer, containing PEG side groups linked to the main chain by bis(terpyridine)ruthenium (II) linkages was successfully prepared (**Figure 9**).

Figure 8. Synthesis of cyclic grafted polymers *via* activated ester amidation (route 1) and CuAAC (route 2) as described by Tew et al.⁴⁴ *Exo*-5-norbornenecarboxylic acid pentafluorophenol ester (M1). The cyclic polyM1 was synthesized using the REMP strategy.

Figure 9. Synthesis of metallo-supramolecular cyclic brush polymer.⁴⁵ The cyclic polyM2 was synthesized using the REMP strategy.

The strategy of utilizing activated pentafluorophenol ester side groups as anchoring points for grafting polymer chains has been expanded to several structures. Examples include grafting PEG and PS chains onto cyclic poly(pentafluorophenyl 4-vinylbenzoate) (cPPF4VB) *via* routes 1 and 2, respectively (**Figure 10a**),⁴⁶ as well as two-arm PS chains onto cPPF4VB *via* route 2, forming a cyclic double-grafted polymer structure (**Figure 10b**).⁴⁷ Another example includes the synthesis of PS-grafted chains onto a cyclic polynorbornene backbone containing activated pentafluorophenol ester side groups using route 2.⁴⁸ The obtained cyclic grafted polymer was evaluated as an emulsion stabilizer, and it was found to exhibit superior interfacial activity in comparison to the linear analog.

Figure 10. Synthesis of different cyclic grafted polymers using the activated pentafluorophenol ester side groups as anchoring points for grafting polymer chains. Grafting (a) PEG and PS chains onto cPPF4VB *via* routes 1 and 2, respectively,⁴⁶ and (b) two-arm PS chains onto cPPF4VB *via* route 2.⁴⁷ The cPPF4VB backbone was synthesized using an RC strategy.

Wu et al.⁴⁹ employed a chiral cyclic Pd (II) catalysts, *rc*-Pd(II) and *sc*-Pd(II), to synthesize cyclic poly(perfluorophenyl 4-isocyanobenzoate) by asymmetric living polymerization, resulting in a one-handed helicity of the backbone (**Figure 11**). Hydroxyl-terminated PS was then grafted onto the cyclic polymer *via* a transesterification reaction on the activated ester side groups. The authors reported quantitative grafting of the side chains while maintaining monomodality. The cyclic brush polymers exhibited toroidal shape with ring diameters ranging from 80 to 200 nm with increasing MW of the polyisocyanide backbone while maintaining the MW of the PS side chains. Interestingly, these series of cyclic brush polymers with a one-handed helical backbone exhibited photoluminescence and circularly polarized luminescence.

Figure 11. Synthesis of cyclic grafted polymer presenting one-handed helicity of the backbone in two steps: synthesis of a cyclic polyisocyanide containing activated

pentafluorophenol ester side groups using chiral cyclic Pd (II) catalysts *via* REP, followed by PS grafting.⁴⁹

Other types of "click" reactions, different from CuAAC, have been employed in the "grafting-onto" strategy for the synthesis of cyclic grafted polymers. Triazolinedione (TAD)-diene based Diels-Alder "click" reaction implemented by Du-Prez et al.⁵⁰ was successfully used for the grafting of multiblocks side chains onto cyclic backbones (**Figure 12**).⁵¹ A cyclic backbone based on poly(norbornene imide) containing diene side groups was first synthesized by REMP. Then, TAD-terminated copolymers based on methacrylate derivative monomers were grafted to the cyclic backbone by recourse of the TAD-diene Diels-Alder reaction. Although the grafting density obtained for one of the grafted copolymers, composed of poly(glycidyl methacrylate)-*block*-poly(oligo(ethylene glycol) methacrylate) (PGMA-*b*-POEGMA), was as high as 91 %, it was significantly reduced for a second copolymer of different composition, poly(3-(triethoxysilyl)propyl methacrylate)-*block*-poly(oligo(ethyleneglycol) methacrylate) (PTEPM-*b*-POEGMA), reaching values of only 49 %. Based on these results and on the fact that both grafting reactions used the same "click" chemistry, it appears that the polymer composition of the grafted units is also relevant to successful grafting in addition to steric hindrance.

Figure 12. Grafting PGMA-*b*-POEGMA and PTEPM-*b*-POEGMA side chains onto a cyclic poly(norbornene imide) backbone *via* TAD-diene based Diels-Alder "click" reaction.⁵¹ The cyclic backbone was synthesized using the REMP strategy.

An efficient amine-thiol-ene "click" reaction⁵² was employed to synthesize cyclic grafted polymers with a Y-junction formed by *N,N*-diethylethylenediamine (DEDA) and PEG groups (**Figure 13**). To generate the grafted Y junctions, the thiolactone units contained in a cyclic copolymer backbone composed of *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM) and *N*-acryloylhomocysteine thiolactone (ATL),⁵³ or styrene and 2-maleimidyl-4-thiobutyrolactone,⁵⁴ were first subjected to aminolysis (e.g., with DEDA⁵³ or *N,N*-dimethylethylenediamine, DMDA⁵⁴) followed by thiol-acrylate Michael addition with poly(ethylene glycol) methyl ether acrylate (PEGA). Such Y-junctions were aimed at introducing additional stimuli-responsive properties into the polymer, in addition to the thermoresponsiveness inherent in PNIPAM⁵³ or the hydrophobicity of the polystyrene

moieties.⁵³ In particular, DEDA is pH sensitive and PEG is able to interact with CO₂ through the ether groups,^{55, 56} providing the polymer with tunable physical properties in solution.

Figure 13. Synthesis of Y-junction using amine-thiol-ene "click" reaction *via* aminolysis of thiolactone side groups with DEDA followed by thiol-acrylate Michael addition with PEGA.⁵³ The cyclic polymer backbone was synthesized using an RC strategy.

Table 1 offers a comprehensive overview of the grafting-onto reactions outlined in this section.

Table 1. Summary of cyclic grafted polymers generated by "grafting-onto" approach.

Monomeric units ^a	Cyclization method	Active group ^b	Grafted chains	Complementary end group ^c	Reaction type	Ref.
ϵ CL and γ Et ₃ SiO ϵ CL	REP	OH	PEO	COOH	esterification	35
chloroethyl vinyl ether	RC	Cl	PS	carbanion	nucleophilic substitution	36
styrene and 4-(3-butenyl)styrene	RC	Cl	PS	carbanion	nucleophilic substitution	37
4-bromostyrene	RC	Br	PS	phenylboronic acid pinacol ester	Suzuki coupling	38
4-acetoxystyrene	RC	alkyne	polyester dendrons	N ₃	CuAAC	42
<i>tert</i> -butyl acrylate	RC	alkyne	PS	N ₃	CuAAC	43
M1	REMP	pentafluorophenol ester	PEG	NH ₂	amidation	44
M1	REMP	alkyne	PEG	N ₃	CuAAC	44

M2	REMP	terpyridine	PEG	terpyridine - Ru(III) complex	metal-chelation	45
M2	REMP	alkyne	PS	N ₃	CuAAC	48
pentafluorophenyl 4-vinylbenzoate	RC	pentafluorophenol ester	PEG	NH ₂	amidation	46
pentafluorophenyl 4-vinylbenzoate	RC	alkyne	PS	N ₃	CuAAC	46
perfluorophenyl 4-isocyanobenzoate	REP	pentafluorophenol ester	PS	OH	transesterification	49
M3	REMP	diene	PGMA- <i>b</i> -POEGMA	TAD	TAD-diene Diels-Alder	51
M3	REMP	diene	PTEPM- <i>b</i> -POEGMA	TAD	TAD-diene Diels-Alder	51
NIPAM and ATL	RC	thiobutylactone	Y-junction: PEG ₈ and DEDA	alkene and NH ₂	amine-thiolene	53
styrene and MTL	RC	thiobutylactone	Y-junction: PEG ₈ and DMDA	alkene and NH ₂	amine-thiolene	54

^aMonomeric units that form the cyclic backbone before side group modification, if applicable. ^bActive group in the cyclic backbone allowing grafting. ^cComplementary reactive end group of the grafted chain. Abbreviations: γ -triethylsilyloxy ϵ -caprolactone (γ Et₃SiO ϵ CL); *exo*-5-norbornenecarboxylic acid pentafluorophenol ester (M1); pentafluorophenol ester-based norbornene imide (M2); hydroxyethyl-derivative norbornene imide (M3); *N*-acryloylhomocysteine thiolactone (ATL); 2-maleimidyl-4-thiobutylactone (MTL).

2.3. Grafting-from approach

In the "grafting-from" approach, radial growth of side chains from the backbone ensures high grafting density by reducing the steric hindrance of the propagating chains. Unlike the "grafting-onto" strategy, there is no need to add higher equivalents of side chains per anchorage site. This eliminates the need for lengthy purification processes. This approach offers high versatility in choosing the backbone and side branches. The "grafting-from" technique is highly effective for preparing cyclic, multiblock-grafted structures,

particularly in cases where the MW of the targeted side chains exceeds the limitations of the “grafting-onto” strategy.

Similar to the synthesis of linear dendronized polymers¹⁹ and the only reported case (as far as we know) of cyclic dendronized polymers synthesized using the grafting-from technique,⁴² the synthesis of grafted dendrons faces several important limitations. With each generation, incomplete reactions can accumulate structural defects that compromise monodispersity. Purification becomes increasingly difficult because impurities are hard to separate from fully branched structures, and yields decrease drastically with each additional generation due to steric congestion. This is probably why the use of the “grafting-from” strategy to generate cyclic dendronized polymers has not been widely explored. Laurent and Grayson⁴² were able to synthesize a styrene-based cyclic polymer backbone with dendritic polyester side chains by growing dendrons in a stepwise fashion up to the third generation using iterative esterification and deprotection chemistry. However, a loss of monomodality was observed at the third generation by GPC, which compared to previous generations remained monomodal. Thus, considerable research efforts are still needed to develop reliable and efficient methods of producing cyclic dendronized polymers *via* the “grafting-from” approach.

As described below, controlled radical polymerization techniques are a powerful synthetic strategy for generating uniform side chains. Other protocols for side-chain growth, such as ring-opening polymerization (ROP) and anionic polymerization, have also been used, albeit to a lesser extent. One of the first reports on the “grafting-from” technique for the synthesis of cyclic grafted structures was made by Huang et al.⁵⁷ (**Figure 14a**). They grafted PS chains onto a cyclic polyether backbone by growing the PS chains from TEMPO side groups through nitroxide-mediated radical polymerization (NMRP) of styrene initiated by benzoyl peroxide (BPO). The efficiency of TEMPO as a co-initiator

was reported to be 100 %, indicating its complete participation in the grafting reaction. The same group later reported the polymerization of styrene initiated from isobutyryl side groups *via* atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP), in which 98% initiation efficiency was reported (**Figure 14b**).⁵⁸ Finally, they reported the ROP of ϵ CL initiated from the hydroxyl pendant groups of the cyclic backbone catalyzed by $\text{Sn}(\text{Oct})_2$ obtaining high monomer conversion and similar experimental and theoretical MWs (**Figure 14c**).⁵⁹

Figure 14. Synthesis of cyclic grafted polymers in Huang’s group by using different initiation types in the grafting-from approach. (a) NMRP of styrene initiated from TEMPO side groups.⁵⁷ (b) ATRP of styrene initiated from isobutyryl side groups.⁵⁸ (c) ROP of ϵ CL initiated from the hydroxyl side groups.⁵⁹ The cyclic backbones (a-c) were produced using an RC strategy.

In 2012, Tew et al. reported the combination of REMP and the “grafting-from” route for the synthesis of cyclic brush polymers with polyester side chains.⁶⁰ A norbornene imide monomer designed to have a terminal OH group (M4, **Figure 15**) was first polymerized using the Grubbs’ catalyst UC-6 (shown in **Figure 3**). The resulting cyclic

macromonomer was then used as a macroinitiator for the ROP of δ -valerolactone (VL), L-lactide (LLA), and ϵ CL catalyzed by 1,5,7-triazabicyclo[4.4.0]dec-5-ene (TBD), demonstrating the versatility of the method to generate polyester brushes.

Figure 15. Synthesis of cyclic brush polymers by growing polyester side chains from hydroxyl side groups *via* ROP of lactones.⁶⁰

An amphiphilic cyclic grafted polymer composed of a perfluorocyclobutyl aryl ether-based cyclic backbone and poly(methacrylic acid) (PMAA) side chains was synthesized by Huang et al.⁶¹ in 2014 (**Figure 16**). The cyclic backbone was first obtained by Cu-catalyzed Glaser coupling *via* RC of end-group modified poly(2-methyl-1,4-bistrifluorovinyloxybenzene). To introduce ATRP initiation sites into the cyclic backbone, the methylaryl groups were monobrominated with *N*-bromo succinimide (NBS) and benzoyl peroxide (BPO). Subsequently, polymerization of *tert*-butyl methacrylate (*t*BMA) was carried out using the aforementioned macroinitiator and CuBr/PMDETA. Finally, the hydrophobic poly(*t*BMA) side chains were converted to the hydrophilic PMAA chains by acid hydrolysis of *t*Bu groups with trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). This work remains the only report to date of the generation of a cyclic grafted polymer based on a fluorinated cyclic backbone.

Figure 16. Synthesis of an amphiphilic cyclic grafted polymer by grafting poly(*t*BMA) side chains *via* ATRP followed by acid hydrolysis of *t*Bu groups.⁶¹

In 2015, cyclic brush polymers composed of a cyclic poly(ethyl glycinate methacrylamide-*st*-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) (poly(EGMA-*st*-HEMA)) backbone and POEGMA side chains were introduced by Pun et al.^{62, 63} (**Figure 17**). The authors called these structures "sunflower" polymers where the "petals" are the side chains. The cyclic backbone was first synthesized by an RC strategy using CuAAC click reaction. Then, after functionalizing the HEMA units with α -bromoisobutyryl bromide, the POEGMA "petals" were grown by ATRP. The resulting polymer was decorated with the cancer-targeting ligand folate on the OEGMA units, and with fluorescein⁶² and doxorubicin (DOX)⁶³ on the EGMA units. They demonstrated that the resulting polymer obtained by the "grafting-from" approach can be suitably post-functionalized with biologically active molecules due to the reduced hindrance of the side chains. "Sunflower" polymers have found application as promising drug delivery systems as described in a following section.

Figure 17. Synthesis of a cyclic grafted polymer (named "sunflower" by the authors) by grafting POEGMA side chains *via* ATRP followed by functionalization of the OEGMA units with the cancer-targeting ligand folate, and of the EGMA units with NHS-fluorescein⁶² and doxorubicin.⁶³ The cyclic backbone was produced using an RC strategy.

In 2016, the synthesis of a series of cyclic brush polymers based on brominated cyclic polystyrene (cPSBr) was reported (**Figure 18**).⁶⁴ First, a cyclic PS (cPS) backbone was synthesized using a CuAAC click reaction of an end-group-modified linear PS. To generate reactive initiation sites on the cPS backbone, the benzylic hydrogen atoms of the styrene units were substituted by bromine using *N*-bromosuccinimide and AIBN, based on the Wohl–Ziegler bromination reaction. The bromine content was varied to 18%, 25%, 32% and 50% by using different reaction conditions. The obtained brominated cPS (cPSBr) was then used as a macroinitiator for the ATRP polymerization of styrene, NIPAM and methyl methacrylate (MMA) to produce the corresponding cyclic brush polymers. To demonstrate the versatility of this strategy, the cPSBr bromides were converted to dithioester RAFT agents, and then used to graft chains composed of PS, PNIPAM, PMMA, poly(methacrylate) (PMA) and poly(vinyl acetate) (PVAc). The

authors referred to cPSBr as a “universal template” due to its versatility in grafting various brush polymers using ATRP and RAFT polymerization strategies.

Figure 18. Brominated cyclic PS used as a macroinitiator for grafting different polymeric side chain by ATRP and RAFT polymerization.⁶⁴ The cPSBr backbone was produced by RC of a linear PS, followed by a bromination reaction.

As illustrated in **Figure 19**, cyclic poly(HEMA) has been extensively used as a macroinitiator to grow a number of homopolymer and multiblock copolymer side chains, including poly(*N,N*-dimethylaminoethyl methacrylate) (pDMAEMA),⁶⁵ PS-*b*-PEO,⁶⁶ PS-*b*-PAA,⁶⁷ PCL-*b*-POEGMA,⁶⁸ and statistical copolymers formed by [2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl]dimethyl-(3-sulfopropyl) (SBMA) and DMAEMA,⁶⁹ and by NIPAM and *N*-hydroxyethylacrylamide (HEAAm).⁷⁰

Figure 19. Synthesis of cyclic grafted polymers starting from cyclic poly(HEMA) as a macroinitiator. (a) Cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PS-*b*-PEO)),⁶⁶ (b) cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PS-*b*-PAA)),⁶⁷ (c) cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PCL-*b*-POEGMA)) with and without disulfide bonds in the junction between PCL and POEGMA blocks,⁶⁸ (d) cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-pDMAEMA),⁶⁵ (e) cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-p(SBMA-*st*-DMAEMA)),⁶⁹ and (f) cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-p(NIPAM-*st*-HEAAm)).⁷⁰ The cyclic poly(HEMA) was produced using an RC strategy.

In 2011, Huang et al. synthesized the amphiphilic cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PS-*b*-PEO)) (Figure 19a).⁶⁶ The esterification reaction of the pendant hydroxyl groups in cyclic

poly(HEMA) with 2-bromoisobutryl bromide activated the cyclic macroinitiator, enabling the growth of PS side chains *via* ATRP of styrene. Then, PS brushes were coupled with TEMPO-ended PEO chains to generate the targeted amphiphilic structure. This synthetic pathway combines "grafting-from" and "grafting-onto" methods, the latter of which achieved 80-85% grafting efficiency. Later in 2021, Weil et al.⁶⁷ used a similar approach to grow PS chains from the ATRP-activated cyclic poly(HEMA) backbone (**Figure 19b**). They constructed cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PS-*b*-PAA)) by growing a second block of P*t*BA from the PS block, followed by acidic hydrolysis to generate the corresponding PAA block. These structures, which were synthesized with various MWs and copolymer compositions, revealed the formation of hierarchical nanostructures *via* self-assembly when placed in water as described in following section.

To develop a polymer that responds to a reductive biological environment, Wei and Liu et al. synthesized in 2018 cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PCL-SS-POEGMA)) (**Figure 19c**) containing a reducible disulfide bond between the two polymer blocks of the side chain.⁶⁸ For comparison, the authors also prepared an identical polymer structure without the disulfide bond. First, ROP of ϵ CL was initiated from the hydroxyl end groups of poly(HEMA). The resulting cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-PCL) was then esterified with a disulfide-based linker previously obtained by esterification between 3,3'-dithiodipropionic acid and 2-bromoisobutyrate at the hydroxyl end groups of PCL. Finally, the terminal brominated brush was used as a macroinitiator for the ATRP of OEGMA, generating the targeted structure.

In 2016, Pun et al. synthesized a polycation capable of binding plasmid DNA by growing pDMAEMA side chains from a cyclic polyHEMA *via* ATRP (**Figure 19d**).⁶⁵ The polymer contains a number of protonable amine groups in its side chains equal to the degree of polymerization of pDMAEMA, which varied from 11 to 22. The structures

formed by complexing negatively charged plasmid DNA with polycations *via* electrostatic interactions are referred to as “polyplexes”. As delineated in the subsequent section, the polyplexes were subjected to gene transfection evaluation.

In 2023, Li et al. obtained zwitterionic cyclic brush copolymers through the statistical copolymerization of the zwitterionic monomer SBMA with DMAEMA (**Figure 19e**).⁶⁹ This process utilized ATRP-activated cyclic poly(HEMA) as a macroinitiator. The superlubricant properties of the family of polymers obtained by varying the DMAEMA / SBMA monomer ratio were further investigated, as explained in a following section. Thermoresponsive cyclic brush copolymers were reported by Wei et al.⁷⁰ using also statistical copolymerization of NIPAM and HEAAm starting from ATRP-activated cyclic poly(HEMA) (**Figure 19f**). The resulting polymers exhibited a lower critical solution temperature (LCST) that was slightly above physiological temperature.

In 2020, Sumerlin et al.⁷¹ reported the synthesis of cyclic polyphenylacetylene by REP which was transformed by bromination into a suitable macroinitiator for the grafting of PS chains or P*t*BA *via* ATRP of styrene on the benzylic positions along the polymer backbone (**Figure 20**). Bromination was performed *via* the electrophilic addition of bromine (Br₂) to the alkenes in the backbone, resulting in the bromination of ~50% of the alkenes. Consequently, the grafting density in this brush polymer type was lower than when polymers contains an initiation site in each repeating unit. Finally, the PS blocks were chain extended with P*t*BA, followed by their acidic hydrolysis to generate PAA blocks. As a result, cyclic poly(phenylacetylene-*g*-(PS-*b*-PAA)) with an amphiphilic character and abilities to self-aggregate in water were generated.⁷²

Figure 20. Brominated cyclic poly(phenylacetylene) for grafting PS-*b*-PAA brushes via ATRP.^{71, 72} Cyclic polyphenylacetylene was first synthesized by REP followed by bromination.

As a few examples from the literature of a living anionic polymerization technique for the growing of side chains, Adachi et al.⁷³ reported in 2019 a grafting-from method for PS side chains (**Figure 21**). The method consisted into the lithiation of a cyclic poly(*p*-methylstyrene) at the tolyl group with *sec*-BuLi assisted by TMEDA generating benzyl-lithium groups. This activated macroinitiator for the anionic vinyl polymerization was then used to polymerize styrene. AFM measurements of the cyclic brush polymer with high MW confirmed the presence of donut-like structures with a diameter of 50-60 nm and uniform size.

Figure 21. Living anionic polymerization employed to grow PS brushes from an anionically-activated cyclic poly(*p*-methyl styrene) backbone.⁷³ Cyclic poly(*p*-methylstyrene) backbone was synthesized using an RC strategy.

Hypergrafting, a grafting-from technique introduced by Frey's group,⁷⁴ involves the use of suitable functional groups as initiators for the ionic polymerization of AB_m monomers, resulting in hyperbranched polymer structures. This protocol has been used to generate hyperbranched polyglycerol (hbPG) structures *via* ring-opening multibranching polymerization (ROMBP) of glycidol. The macroinitiators used in this process include hbPG itself,^{75, 76} linear polymers,⁷⁷ SiO₂ surfaces,⁷⁸ and carbon-based structures such as nanodiamonds⁷⁹ and multiwall carbon nanotubes.⁸⁰ Recently, in our group we have reported the first synthesis of a cyclic grafted polymer consisting on a cyclic polyglycidol (cPG) backbone and hbPG branches (cPG-*g*-hbPG) *via* hypergrafting.⁸¹ First, the cPG precursor was obtained by electrophilic zwitterionic ring expansion polymerization (eZREP) of *tert*-butyl glycidyl ether (*t*BGE) initiated by B(C₆F₅)₃ followed by the acidic cleavage of the *t*Bu side groups (**Figure 22**).^{81, 82} Then, the hydroxyl side groups of cPG were activated by NaH to promote the ROMBP of glycidol, generating a series of cPG-*g*-hbPG with different MW of the hbPG side units. AFM measurements of a high MW (~1 MDa) cPG-*g*-hbPG confirmed the formation of spherical structures with diameters of about 25 nm. Because of the low MW of the cPG backbone (approximately five monomeric units) and the relatively large size of the branches, spherical structures were anticipated rather than the donut-like structures observed in previous studies.

Figure 22. Synthesis of cPG-*g*-hbPG by hypergrafting from a cPG macroinitiator.⁸¹ cPtBGE was synthesized by ZREP.

Table 2 summarizes the variety of cyclic grafted polymer using grafting-from techniques.

Table 2. Summary of cyclic grafted polymers generated by “grafting-from” approach.

Monomeric units ^a	Cyclization	Initiation group ^b	Grafted chains	Polymerization technique	Ref.
EO and GTEMPO	RC	TEMPO	PS	NMRP	57
EO and EEGE	RC	Br	PS	ATRP	58
EO and EEGE	RC	OH	PCL	ROP	59
M4	REP	OH	PVL, PLLA, PCL	ROP	60
MBTVB	RC	Br	Poly(<i>t</i> BMA) (PMAA) ^c	ATRP	61
EGMA and HEMA	RC	Br	Poly(OEGMA)	ATRP	62, 63
styrene	RC	Br	PNIPAM, PS, PMMA	ATRP	64
styrene	RC	pyrrole dithioester	PNIPAM, PS, PMMA, PMA	RAFT	64
styrene	RC	ethoxyethyl dithioester	PVAc	RAFT	64
HEMA	RC	Br	pDMAEMA	ATRP	65
HEMA	RC	Br	PS (PS- <i>b</i> -PEO) ^d	ATRP	66
HEMA	RC	Br	PS- <i>b</i> - <i>Pt</i> BA (PS- <i>b</i> -PAA) ^e	ATRP	67
HEMA	RC	OH	PCL	ROP	68
HEMA	RC	Br	PCL- <i>b</i> -POEGMA	ATRP	68
HEMA	RC	Br	Poly(SBMA- <i>st</i> - DMAEMA)	ATRP	69
HEMA	RC	Br	Poly(NIPAM- <i>st</i> - HEAAm)	ATRP	70
phenylacetylene	REP	Br	PS, PBA	ATRP	71
phenylacetylene	REP	Br	PS- <i>b</i> - <i>Pt</i> BA (PS- <i>b</i> -PAA) ^e	ATRP	72
<i>p</i> -methylstyrene	RC	benzyl lithium	PS	living anionic polymerization	73
<i>t</i> BGE	ZREP	OH	hbPG	ROMBP	81

^aMonomeric units that form the cyclic backbone before side group modification, if applicable. ^bActive group in the cyclic backbone allowing grafting. ^cPMAA generated by deprotection of *t*Bu groups. ^dPS-*b*-PEO was further generated through the addition of TEMPO-PEO to Br-terminated PS side chains *via* a “grafting-onto” strategy. ^ePS-*b*-PAA generated by deprotection of *t*Bu groups. Abbreviations: ethylene oxide (EO); 1-ethoxyethyl glycidyl ether (EEGE); 4-glycidyloxy-2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl (GTEMPO); hydroxyoctyl-derivative norbornene imide (M4); 2-methyl-1,4-bistrifluorovinyloxybenzene (MBTVB).

2.4. Monomer approach

The “monomer approach” is a relatively new and unconventional area of exploration. Notably, only a few examples of this synthetic approach have been reported thus far. There is generally no single best method for all situations since each method has its own advantages and disadvantages, as well as different applicability depending on the synthesis conditions.

Zwitterionic ring-opening polymerization (ZROP) is nowadays an established method for the synthesis of cyclic polymers.^{5, 13} It can be initiated nucleophilically, with *N*-heterocyclic carbene (NHC), pyridines and amidines, or electrophilically with B(C₆F₅)₃. Lactides, 4, 6, and 7-membered cyclic lactones are monomers susceptible to nucleophilic ZROP (nZROP),^{83, 84} while epoxides are susceptible to electrophilic ZROP.^{85, 86} This method is also called ZREP because it relies on the formation mechanism of cycles. Propagating species consist of zwitterionic intermediates that maintain cyclic structures through electrostatic interactions between chain ends. The catalyst is then regenerated through an intramolecular ring closure.

eZROP (or eZREP) of glycidol was first performed in our group in 2014⁸⁵ as part of a proof of concept for generating cyclic polyethers using B(C₆F₅)₃. Then, in 2022, Lee et al.,²⁵ and our group²⁶ found that the cyclic polymer structure consisted of branched cyclic polyglycerol (bcPG), a special type of cyclic grafted polymer (**Figure 23**). The polymerization occurs in a one-pot reaction and can be scaled to several grams of polymer. Cyclization occurs through a ZREP mechanism and branching reactions occur concurrently *via* nucleophilic attacks of the formed polymers' hydroxyl side groups to the active chains. For that reason, the size of the bcPG backbone ring cannot be determined in advance, nor at the end, in contrast to previous synthesis methods for cyclic grafted polymers, which utilize well-defined initial cyclic polymers. Since the MW does not

conform to the prediction of ionic polymerizations based on monomer to catalyst ratio, caused by the re-initiation of new polymer chains upon catalyst release, the MW of bcPG is difficult to control. For this reason, monitoring the reaction as a function of time, at a certain temperature (0 °C or below), is the only way to determine the MW for each specific reaction.⁸⁷

bcPG can be obtained under bulk or semi-bulk conditions (17 %v/v of solvent),²⁶ or in solution during the initial stages of polymerization.^{25, 87} In semi-bulk conditions, a slight dependence of the M_n of bcPG with the polarity of the solvent was observed.²⁶ In general, the lower the solvent polarity (e.g. *p*-xylene and benzene), the higher the observed MW, which is likely associated with reduced ionic dissociation of the zwitterionic pair. When polymerization is conducted in a solvent (e.g. toluene),^{25, 87} it is initiated in solution but then, the formed oligomers precipitate and continue growing in the precipitated phase, finally reaching a similar MW to that obtained in bulk polymerization.⁸⁷ Lee et al.,²⁵ used the regeneration of $B(C_6F_5)_3$ to demonstrate recyclable catalytic polymerization in solution. The highest MW achieved for bcPG, either in bulk or in solution is about 10 kg/mol ($\bar{D} \sim 2$).^{26, 88} Fractionation using fractional precipitation allows generating bcPG fractions with M_w up to 40 kg/mol, low dispersity values ($\bar{D} \sim 1.3$) and degree of branching of 0.48.^{26, 88}

The characterization of the bcPG structure through the host-guest interactions with two fluorescent probes (PRODAN and coumarin C120) revealed a strong resemblance to crown ethers, confirming the cyclic structure of the core.⁸⁹ However, this method cannot measure the core size. The dependence of the radius of gyration (R_g) on the MW of bcPG structures in a water solution indicates that they are randomly branched.⁸⁸ Due to the prevalence of chain fusion reactions during polymerization in the absence of free glycidol,

the MW continuously increases. This increase in MW can occur in both the cyclic core and the branches, creating a polydisperse polymer in terms of both core and branch sizes.

Figure 23. Synthesis of bcPG *via* the “monomer approach” consisting of a one-pot eZREP of glycidol with $B(C_6F_5)_3$.^{25, 26, 87}

Lee et al.⁹⁰ also performed the eZREP of glycidol using frustrated Lewis pairs (FLPs) as catalysts. They combined $B(C_6F_5)_3$ with two types of amines: tributylamine and pyridine. Only the FLP formed by $B(C_6F_5)_3$ and pyridine conducted to the formation of bcPG. This result was attributed to the lower steric effect of pyridine compared to tributylamine leading to enhanced stabilization of the zwitterionic intermediate during propagation. More recently, the same group demonstrated that, using the $Cu(\text{triNHC})$ catalyst, bcPG can be obtained, albeit with a much lower degree of branching than that obtained using $B(C_6F_5)_3$ and FLPs, with values as low as 0.08 compared to ~ 0.5 obtained using the other catalysts.⁹¹

3. Structure-property relationship of cyclic grafted polymers

3.1. Physical properties

Many of the expected properties of these polymer structures arise from both their highly dense macromolecular architectures and the cyclic center. The high conformational rigidity resulting from the high grafting density endows grafted polymers with a defined

shape and size in the order of nanometers.^{18, 92, 93} This property renders AFM optimal for the visualization and measurement of shape parameters of grafted structures, including ring diameter, side chain length, grafting completion and topological purity. **Figure 24** exhibits the AFM data of PCVE-*g*-PS reported by Schappacher and Deffieux in 2008.⁹⁴ The cyclic comb polymers were obtained by grafting living polystyrene onto PCEVE chains in accordance with their previously established methods.³⁶ The authors found that the cyclic backbone diameter corresponded to an almost fully stretched ring, and the measured circumference was close to that calculated for a completely extended chain, where the C-C bond length is 0.25 nm. Additionally, the ring section expanded as the DP of the PS side chains increased. This is consistent with the observation of densely packed side chains around the cyclic backbone. Nowadays, AFM is one of the most widely used techniques for characterizing and the directly visualizing cyclic grafted structures.^{28, 29, 44, 45, 49, 67, 73, 81, 95}

Figure 24. AFM images and section analysis of purified PCEVE-*g*-PS structures. DP of cyclic PCEVE backbone of (a,b) 548, (c) 774 and (d) 956 and M_n of PS side chains of (a,

c) 10.7 and (b, d) 17.9 kg/mol. Adapted with permission from 94. Copyright 2008, American Chemical Society.

It is commonly found in the literature the determination of the “g” factor, which establishes the ratio of R_g of the cyclic polymers to that of linear polymers with an identical MW. This ratio, $g = \langle R_{g,c}^2 \rangle / \langle R_{g,l}^2 \rangle$, is used as a measure of the ring compaction and to confirm the formation of cyclic polymers in synthetic studies. The relationship $\langle R_{g,c}^2 \rangle = 1/2 \langle R_{g,l}^2 \rangle$ was theoretically calculated by Kramers⁹⁶ and Zimm and Stockmayer.⁹⁷ However, this relationship does not apply to small rings that do not satisfy the statistical basis of the calculation. Experimentally, large variations of the “g” factor have been reported from 0.5 to 0.6 for well-studied PS rings.⁹⁸⁻¹⁰⁰ These variations found in the literature have been attributed to different solvent conditions, as well as to sample purity.

Schappacher and Deffieux⁹⁴ found for the cyclic brush polymers shown in **Figure 24**, that the “g” factor was close to 0.5 in very good agreement with the theoretical predictions and experimental data of cyclic PS.¹⁰⁰ The authors noted that, in comb structures, the overall chain architecture plays a more dominant role than other parameters. This may be because the grafting process amplifies the linear and cyclic polymers equally, thus maintaining their inherent characteristics.

The structural parameter used for grafted polymers is defined by $g' = \langle R_{branched}^2 \rangle / \langle R_{non-branched}^2 \rangle$, where $R_{branched}^2$ is the mean-square radius of the branched polymer and $R_{non-branched}^2$ is the mean-square radius of the analogous non-branched polymer with the same MW. g' is referred to as the branching parameter or contraction factor, it is never equal to zero; rather, it is approximately 0.1 at high degrees of branching and never exceeds 1.¹⁰¹ Matsushita et al.³⁷ found smaller g' values for cyclic

PS-*g*-PS than for their linear analogues confirming that variation in backbone chain architecture affects polymer dimensions. Li et al.⁴³ provided another example when they found that cyclic poly(propargyl acrylate-*g*-PS) had a smaller g' than the linear brush analog with a similar grafting density. In our studies, we found that the R_g of the bcPG structures shown in **Figure 23**, as measured by small angle x-ray scattering (SAXS) in water, was slightly smaller by a factor of 1.14 than that of a mixture of bcPG and linear branched PG structures obtained when water was present in the reaction.⁸⁸

GPC characterization is a straightforward and advantageous method for determining chain compaction. The GPC elution time is related to the molecular size in a given solvent and therefore the relationship between the relative and absolute MW (MW_{rel}/MW_{abs}) can be used to conduct compaction studies.^{43, 102} In our group we found that the cPG-*g*-hbPG (see **Figure 22** for their synthesis) had smaller MW_{rel}/MW_{abs} values than analogous structures derived from a linear backbone or a trifunctional core.⁸¹ This indicates a higher degree of compaction within the detectable low-to-mid MW range. At very high MW ($\sim 10^6$ g/mol) no notable differences were found among the structures because the GPC column could not discriminate between them by hydrodynamic volume.

Cyclic polymers typically have higher T_g values than their linear counterparts in the low-to-mid range of MW. This is due to their higher degree of compaction and restricted mobility, as well as the absence of chain-end entropic contribution. At very high MWs this effect becomes negligible. The presence of side chains in cyclic grafted polymers will certainly modify the T_g of the cyclic backbone. An increase in T_g may result from restricted segmental mobility caused by dense packing of side chains, which limits the flexibility of the grafted chains and the backbone. High grafting density and long side chains will enhance this effect. However, the exact change in T_g will depend on the chemical compatibility between the backbone and side chains, the grafting density and

the MW of both the backbone and the side chains.^{93, 103} It is also well known that the nature of end groups dramatically affects the T_g , with increases in T_g following increases in chain-end polarities.¹⁰⁴ An even larger increase in T_g was observed when groups capable of hydrogen bonding such as phenol or carboxylic acid were placed at the chain ends.¹⁰⁴ As Monteiro et al.¹⁰⁵ noted, “The chain ends [lowering the T_g] have a much greater influence on T_g than having a single branch point [increasing the T_g] even with greater crowding of chains at that branch for the various topologies”. Therefore, a number of factors govern the T_g 's behavior in branched structures. If all these factors are the same in the cyclic and linear grafted structures of same MW, it might be then expected that the topology of the backbone have an additional effect on T_g and that can be attributed directly to the backbone.

Some studies have indicated increased⁶⁴ and decreased T_g ³⁸ values for the cyclic grafted structures relative to their cyclic backbone. In the first example, the grafted structures were formed by PS, PNIPAM or PMMA side chains ($M_n > 3.5$ kg/mol) that were directly grafted from a cyclic PS backbone with a similar MW ($M_n = 4$ kg/mol) *via* the “grafting-from” strategy.⁶⁴ In the second example, PS chains ($M_n = 2.8$ kg/mol) were connected through a rigid biphenyl group to a cyclic PS backbone of similar MW ($M_n = 3.3$ kg/mol) using the “grafting-onto” strategy. While it is difficult to explain this behavior of the T_g , one might consider that the biphenyl group connecting the side chains to the backbone could somehow affect side chain packing and chain mobility due to the restricted rotational motions of this group.

A similar situation was observed when comparing cyclic grafted chains with their linear grafted analogues, with increasing^{53, 54} or decreasing T_g ³¹ values. In the first two examples, the side groups consist of a Y-junction composed by small-size PEO (DP = 8) and short DEDA⁵³ or PEGA⁵⁴ units connected to a polyamide copolymer backbone with

a $M_n = 12$ kg/mol (formed by NIPAM and ATL prior grafting, **Figure 13**). These findings confirm that the effect of cyclic topology on T_g persists, as evidenced by a higher T_g in the cyclic precursor compared to the linear one.⁵³ In the second example, the polymerization was performed *via* the “grafting-through” method using a 4.6 kg/mol macromonomer containing a polymerizable norbornene imide unit and PS (**Figure 3**). The M_n of the cyclic and linear grafted polymers was 250 and 200 kg/mol, respectively. This implies that the backbone size is slightly larger in the ring ($DP_{\text{ring}} = 54$ vs. $DP_{\text{linear}} = 43$), while the DP of the PS side chain remains at 43. It is unclear whether the effect of the cyclic backbone on the T_g persists when the side-chain and backbone sizes are similar, and the backbone size is large enough.³¹

Our group conducted a comprehensive comparison of the T_g of various polyglycerol samples with different grafted topologies and a broad MW range (**Figure 25**).⁸¹ Upon hypergrafting glycidol from cyclic and linear polyglycidol macroinitiators (“grafting-from” approach), the backbone size was maintained ($DP_{\text{ring}} = 5$ and $DP_{\text{linear}} = 7$, respectively). Consequently, mass growth occurred at the expense of branch size in cPG-*g*-hbPG and the analogous linear (linPG-*g*-hbPG) samples. Additionally, a series of hbPG and bcPG samples were compared: hbPG was synthesized by ROMBP from 1,1,1-tris(hydroxymethyl)propane (TMP)⁸¹ and bcPG was synthesized by ZREP with $B(C_6F_5)_3$ (monomer approach) (**Figure 23**).²⁶ hbPG samples are compact, globular structures containing a TMP nucleus, while bcPG samples are randomly branched structures formed by a ring backbone of variable size. In the latter, mass growth occurs at the expense of both the ring backbone and the branches. The T_g data of cPG-*g*-hbPG, linPG-*g*-hbPG and hbPG show minimal variation with MW, which is consistent with the formation of effective “cross-linking” due to hydrogen bonding.¹⁰⁶ In this series, the glass transition temperature for infinite MW, T_g^∞ , was observed to be highest for cPG-*g*-hbPG ($T_g^\infty = 269$

K) suggesting that the backbone topology significantly affects the packing of polymer segments, and, consequently renders the segmental mobility more difficult. It is plausible that chain crowding in the vicinity of the small ring backbone is of a particularly elevated nature. As the radial distance from the center increases, it is expected that the packing constraints will become more relaxed. However, this phenomenon does not appear to be reflected in the observed data. Furthermore, bcPG samples demonstrated a significant increase in T_g with M_n , which can be adequately described by the Kanig-Ueberreiter equation.¹⁰⁷ In contrast with cPG-*g*-hbPG, the steric constraints near the core and the number of branching points vary with MW in this series of samples. These disparities become more pronounced at low MW. Conversely, at elevated MW, the T_g values of bcPG approach that of cPG-*g*-hbPG.

Figure 25. T_g obtained from differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments as a function of MW for a series of polyglycerol structures obtained by hypergrafting glycidol from cyclic (cPG-*g*-hbPG) and linear (linPG-*g*-hbPG) polyglycidol.⁸¹ Comparison with an hbPG structure obtained by ROMBP⁸¹ and bcPG obtained by ZREP.²⁶ The dashed lines correspond to the Kanig-Ueberreiter equation fits.¹⁰⁷ Adapted with permission from

3.2. Self-assembly

Cyclic copolymers exhibit distinct and remarkable self-assembly behavior compared to their linear analogues, a phenomenon favored by their compact cyclic structure.^{108, 109} Their behavior has been found to differ from that of their linear counterparts in the formation of micellar structures with smaller hydrodynamic radius (R_h),¹¹⁰⁻¹¹² higher critical micelle concentration (CMC) values,^{111, 112} as well as smaller aggregation numbers (N_{agg}).^{112, 113} Higher thermal¹¹⁴ and salt stabilities^{114, 115} were also found for micellar systems formed by cyclic copolymers.

Cyclic grafted copolymers exhibit a combination of properties reminiscent of both cyclic copolymers^{108, 109} and bottlebrush polymers,^{116, 117} a feat attributable to the flexibility afforded by the side chains in terms of composition and length. In 2008 Schappacher and Deffieux⁹⁵ demonstrated that densely grafted, high MW cyclic brush copolymers self-assembled into well-defined polymeric nanotubes (**Figure 26**). The cyclic backbone was composed of PCEVE randomly grafted with PS and polyisoprene (PI). When dispersed in n-heptane, a selective solvent for PI, the cyclic brush copolymers self-assembled into nanotubes with a diameter of approximately 100 nm and a length of up to 600 nm. The nanotube diameter closely matched that of the individual cyclic brush polymers, indicating that self-assembly occurred *via* cofacial stacking of the cyclic structures.

Figure 26. (a) AFM phase image of tubular objects formed by self-assembly of cyclic PCEVE randomly grafted with PS/PI brushes. The sample was deposited on highly oriented pyrolytic graphite from heptane solution. (b) Schematic representation of tubular assemblies. Adapted with permission from 95. Copyright 2008, The American Association for the Advancement of Science.

In 2016, O'Reilly et al.¹¹⁸ investigated the solution conformation and cloud point for cyclic grafted copolymers with a polycarbonate backbone and poly(*N*-acryloylmorpholine) (PNAM) side chains of varying lengths. Comprehensive SAXS studies, along with dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements, revealed significant differences in the conformations of cyclic and linear graft copolymers in solution. In water, both copolymer types form unimolecular micellar structures that are spherical when the PNAM arms are relatively short. As the PNAM arm length increases from a DP of 30 to 110, the cyclic grafted copolymers transition to an elongated shape. Meanwhile, the linear graft copolymers retain their spherical geometry across all investigated compositions. This different solution conformation was also reflected on a significant difference (approximately 20 °C) in the cloud point between the cyclic and linear graft copolymers. Interestingly, mixtures of cyclic and linear graft copolymers exhibited a single cloud point transition, suggesting cooperative thermoresponsive behavior between

the two types of graft copolymers. However, the cloud point temperatures were not proportional to the ratio of each polymer.

In 2021, Weil et al.⁶⁷ studied the aggregation behavior of cyclic poly(HEMA) and their grafted structures containing amphiphilic PS-*b*-PAA side chains (**Figure 19b**). Cyclic poly(HEMA) formed stable wormlike assemblies in water while their linear analogues generated gel-like precipitates (**Figure 27a**). The cyclic grafted polymers were found to aggregate into stable wormlike and higher-ordered network structures at concentrations of 0.4 mg/mL (**Figure 27b**). A decrease in the weight fraction of PAA resulted in an increase in the length of these assemblies. Conversely, a linear graft analogue exhibited an inability to form ordered structures, accompanied by precipitation observed at similar concentration.

Figure 27. (a) TEM image of the worm-like self-assembled structures of cyclic poly(HEMA) and molecular dynamics simulation snapshot showing self-assembly. (b) AFM and TEM images of hierarchical structures obtained through the self-assembly of cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PS-*b*-PAA)). Molecular dynamics simulations showing self-assembly on the left (hydrophobic backbones) and on the right (full molecules). Adapted with permission from 67. Copyright 2021 The Authors Published by Springer Nature.

In 2022, Sumerlin et al.⁷² studied the self-assembly behavior of amphiphilic cyclic poly(phenylacetylene-*g*-(PS-*b*-PAA)) (**Figure 20**). They observed a transition from spherical nanoparticles to multiporous spheres to nanoparticles with a single pore (also called nanobowls) when water was incrementally added to a polymer solution in THF,

ranging from 10% to 60% (**Figure 28**). However, faster water addition to reach 71% water content resulted in only multiporous spheres, without forming nanobowls, indicating a process dominated by kinetics. This shape transformation was attributed to a change in the internal viscosity of the nanoparticles during the solvent exchange process, wherein smaller solvent droplets coalesce into one pore. The linear grafted analogue exhibited distinct behavior. When water was slowly added to the THF polymer solution, only multi-porous nanoparticles were detected, indicating the occurrence of topological effects.

Figure 28. (top) Proposed schematic representation of nanobowl formation where increased % water content leads to a morphological change from spheres to porous spheres and finally to nanobowls, as the pores coalesce into one large void. (a-c) SEM images of the nanoparticles at different % water content. Adapted with permission from 72. Copyright 2022 American Chemical Society.

In addition to the self-assembly of cyclic grafted copolymers, examples of self-assembly involving other cyclic architectures have been reported. These include tadpole-shaped amphiphilic copolymers with a cyclic backbone and one¹¹⁹⁻¹²² or two^{121, 123} tails, as well

as planar cyclic peptides oppositely grafted with two polymer chains (one hydrophilic and one hydrophobic).¹²⁴⁻¹²⁷ The latter cases, developed in Perrier's research group have demonstrated the formation of cylindrical micelles, which they called tubisome based on the terms liposome and polymersome, with significant biomedical application potential. **Figure 29** exhibits one of these examples, where a cyclic peptide was modified by the attachment of an hydrophobic segment composed of PnBA, and an hydrophilic segment composed of PEG chains grafted onto a polyacrylate backbone, forming poly(PEG acrylate).¹²⁴ The formation of strong hydrogen bonds by cyclic peptides results in the formation of multiple stacks of peptides and a hydrophobic cavity capable of carrying drugs.¹²⁷ The conjugates of these cyclic peptides and amphiphilic polymer blocks result in the tubisome self-assemblies. It was also found that the hydrophilic polymer has no major influence on the self-assembly process, though it can be varied to increase the size of the surrounding corona of the cylindrical micelles.¹²⁵

Figure 29. Structure of amphiphilic cyclic peptide/polymer conjugate and self-assembly into tubisomes developed in Perrier's research group.¹²⁴ Adapted with permission from 124. Copyright 2018 Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co.

4. Biomedical applications of cyclic grafted polymers

In the domain of biomedicine, cyclic grafted polymers have emerged as a promising class of materials, owing to their distinctive structural characteristics and the versatility of their

physicochemical properties, which can be tuned to suit specific requirements. It is noteworthy that cyclic grafted polymers have demonstrated considerable promise in the fields of drug delivery and gene transfection. In these applications, their capacity to enhance circulation time, cellular uptake, and targeting efficiency can be exploited to facilitate more effective and selective therapeutic interventions.

In 2009 Fréchet, Szoka et al.^{128, 129} investigated the effect of backbone topology and MW on their circulation times in blood and tumor uptake in mice. They obtained water-soluble, cyclic grafted polymers by grafting PEG side chains to cyclic PLC¹²⁸ or cyclic PAA¹²⁹ backbones. They demonstrated that cyclic grafted polymers with a MW greater than the renal filtration threshold had longer circulation times than their linear analogues. They attributed these results to reduced renal clearance dominated by distinct diffusion mechanisms through kidney nanopores. Unlike cyclic polymers, which lack chain ends and require deformation to pass through pores, linear polymers can more easily reptate through kidney nanopores. Furthermore, higher concentrations of cyclic PEGylated PAA were observed in tumor cells after 48 h compared to the linear analogue.¹²⁹ These results suggest that the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect in cyclic branched polymers exhibit structure-dependent behavior, a phenomenon also observed in dendrimeric structures.¹³⁰ The impact of cyclic grafted polymers on blood circulation profiles and the EPR effect could form the basis for targeted or differentiated drug delivery systems.

In 2021 Jiang et al.²⁰ evaluated the effect of the topology of cyclic PEGylated poly(norbornene) with MW $\sim 10^6$ g/mol on several biological parameters in *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments. In contrast to previous studies obtained by Fréchet, Szoka et al.,^{128, 129} shorter blood circulation times and higher liver and spleen uptake were observed for the cyclic grafted polymer compared to its analogous linear structure. These findings were

ascribed to increased protein adsorption on the cyclic structure. One plausible explanation for this phenomenon is that the lower flexibility of the cyclic polymer promotes more stable protein binding. Consequently, the interplay between polymer architecture and biological interactions emerges as a pivotal factor in delineating *in vivo* behavior.

In 2024, our group evaluated the ability of bcPG (see **Figure 23** for their synthesis) to cross an *in vitro* blood–brain barrier (BBB) model using hCMEC/D3 cells.⁸⁸ The BBB is a highly selective, protective physiological barrier formed by specialized endothelial cells that tightly control the movement of substances from the bloodstream into the brain. This process preserves the brain's distinct microenvironment, which is essential for normal neural function. In the model, the endothelial permeability (EP) of fluorescently-labeled bcPG with rhodamine B (RhB) was monitored using a transwell model of the BBB (**Figure 30a**). To provide a basis for comparison, other fluorescently-labeled polyglycerol structures were also monitored, including a globular hbPG of similar MW and a mixture of bcPG and its branched linear polyglycerol (blPG) analog concurrently obtained during the synthesis of bcPG by the addition of water. The results demonstrated that the bcPG exhibited the lowest EP value compared to the other structures, thereby indicating a topological effect in crossing this biological barrier (**Figure 30b**). Confocal images of the endothelial cells confirmed that BBB crossing occurred through the cells and not through the cell junctions. Furthermore, these images demonstrated that bcPG was mainly localized around cell nuclei, while hbPG was not. The hypothesis underlying these results was predicated on the notion that the topological differences in polyglycerol structures, resulting from their varied shapes and sizes in a water enriched environment, could potentially influence their interaction with cell membranes, and subsequently the EP. bcPG is characterized by a cyclic core with randomly grown branches, while hbPG is formed by a tridentate nucleus with homogeneously distributed branches, and bcPG is

more compact (smaller R_g) than bc+bIPG. Additionally, our findings indicated that bcPG exhibited less cytotoxic effect compared to the other polyglycerol structures. Overall, our results suggest potential applications of bcPG structures in brain delivery systems and underscore the significance of polymer topology in BBB crossing *in vitro*.

Figure 30. Endothelial permeability (EP) of polyglycerol structures in a transwell model of the BBB. (a) Scheme of the transwell system used to mimic the BBB. (b) EP of RhB-labeled polyglycerol structures with different topologies calculated by measuring the fluorescence in the “brain” side compartment over time (up to 3 h, at 37 °C). 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of RhB- labeled polyglycerol was added to the “blood” compartment. Data are expressed as the mean \pm SD of at least three independent measurements, each of which is in triplicate. (c) Confocal images showing RhB-labeled polyglycerol passage through the transwell model made by hCMEC/D3. HPG = hbPG in this review, and bc+bIPG is a mixture of bcPG and branched linear polyglycerol. Adapted with permission from 88. Copyright 2024 The Authors. Published by American Chemical Society.

In the field of drug delivery, cyclic grafted polymers have emerged as promising drug carriers, either covalently attached to the structure⁶³ or present in micellar aggregates.⁶⁸⁻

⁷⁰ The “sunflower” polymers consisting of cyclic poly(EGMA-*st*-HEMA) grafted with POEGMA side chains (**Figure 17**)⁶³ were evaluated as a drug carrier for DOX. The DOX molecules were covalently attached to the foliated-modified “sunflower” *via* a pH-sensitive linker. At a pH of 5.5, which is comparable to the pH of late endosomes and lysosomes, 74% of DOX was released from the polymer after 24 h. In comparison, at a physiological pH of 7.4, only 6.5 % of the DOX was released over 4 days. The results of the intracellular trafficking studies indicated that the polymer is internalized through an endocytosis mechanism, where it is likely that drug release occurs. A comparative analysis was performed on analogous linear grafted polymer; however, this analysis was not extended to the drug release properties. Instead, it focused on the cytotoxicities of polymer structures utilizing human cancer cells (KB and A549). The utilization of these cell lines is predicated on the determination of whether cellular uptake is specifically mediated by the folate receptor, as has been demonstrated to occur for the “sunflower”.⁶² In the course of the experiments, a selective cell-killing phenomenon for KB cells over A549 cells was observed for the “sunflower”. In contrast, no such selectivity was observed for the analogous linear grafted polymer.

Cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PCL-*b*-POEGMA)) (**Figures 19c**) and cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-*p*(NIPAM-*st*-HEAAm)) (**Figure 19f**) were studied as stimuli-responsive micelle for the release of DOX *in vitro*.^{68, 70} Cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-(PCL-*b*-POEGMA)) forms unimolecular micelles in water with diameters ranging from 33 to 43 nm, as the DP of the POEGMA block increases within a wide range of polymer concentrations.⁶⁸ The presence of disulfide bonds in the junction between the PCL and POEGMA blocks in the side chains facilitated the detachment of the hydrophilic POEGMA block in a reductive environment. This detachment destabilizes the unimolecular micelles and forms larger aggregates. DOX-loaded micelles formed by the polymer containing disulfide bonds

released a higher concentration of the drug and exhibited higher therapeutic efficiency against HeLa cells than analogous polymer without reducible group. Cyclic poly(HEMA-*g-p*(NIPAM-*st*-HEAAm)) forms unimolecular nanoparticles with a diameter of 28 nm in phosphate buffer at pH 7.4 and temperatures ranging from 35 to 37 °C.⁷⁰ However, their size dramatically increases to 2 μm at temperatures above 39 °C due to the LCST behavior of the thermoresponsive poly(NIPAM-*st*-HEAAm) brushes. An analogous grafted linear polymer exhibited a lower critical aggregation concentration and a higher nanoparticle diameter of 40 nm. However, their temperature-dependent behavior was similar. Consequently, the release profile for DOX at the various temperatures tested around LCST exhibited similarity for both topologies, cyclic and linear grafted polymers. When tested *in vitro*, DOX-loaded micelles formed by the cyclic grafted polymer exhibited a higher therapeutic efficiency against HeLa cells than analogous linear grafted polymer, likely associated to a faster drug release kinetics.

Zwitterionic cyclic poly(HEMA-*g-p*(SBMA-*st*-DMAEMA)) (**Figure 19e**) was evaluated as a pH-responsive anti-inflammatory drug delivery platform for the dual release of the hydrophobic compound curcumin (Cur) and the hydrophilic compound loxoprofen sodium (LXP), which are used to treat osteoarthritis, in *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments.⁶⁹ The polymer self-aggregates to form spherical micelles in water and in a buffer of pH 7.4 with increasing hydrodynamic diameters from 70 to 120 nm as the amount of DMAEMA relative to SBMA increases. At a pH of 5.5, a destabilization of the micellar structures occurs. In comparison with a linear grafted analogue, the cyclic topology demonstrated higher drug loading and encapsulation rate, as well as higher concurrent release rate of both Cur and LXP at pH 5.5 over a 14-day period. At a pH of 7.4, the release of both drugs also occurs concurrently, with the linear grafted analogue exhibiting a marginally higher release rate. The presence of both charges ($-N^+(CH_3)_2-$ and $-SO_3^-$) in the side

chains of the grafted polymers enables their ability to uptake significant amounts of water, subsequently forming hydrated lubricating layers. Furthermore, the authors evaluated the protective effect of dual (Cur and LXP) drug-loaded micelles on chondrocyte using lipopolysaccharide-activated inflammation models in *in vitro* experiments. The results demonstrated that the drug-loaded micelles formed by the cyclic grafted polymer induced more significant changes in the expression levels of the six analyzed genes compared to the rest of the analyzed reference samples. The observed outcomes were ascribed to the enhanced lubricant properties of the cyclic grafted polymer and the dual-drug anti-inflammatory activity. *In vivo* experiments demonstrated that dual-drug-loaded micelles formed by the cyclic grafted polymer significantly reduced osteophyte volume (54.5% vs. 39.4 % for the linear analogue) and inhibited cartilage degeneration.

Cyclic poly(HEMA-*g*-pDMAEMA) (**Figure 19d**) was complexed with a luciferase reporter plasmid at various polymer amine-to-DNA phosphate (N/P) ratios to form polyplexes for gene delivery evaluation in HeLa human cervical cancer cells.⁶⁵ The hydrodynamic diameter of the complexes with an N/P ratio of 5 exhibited a variation from 115 to 135 nm as the DP of the pDMAEMA side chain increased. This phenomenon was attributed to the enhanced ability of the complex to condense into spherical structures. Additionally, polyplexes formed by cyclic grafted polymers exhibited smaller hydrodynamic diameters than their linear brush analogues. The transfection efficiency of the polyplexes increased with the N/P ratio from 3 to 5, and decreased with an N/P of 7, a phenomenon that was attributed to the toxicity of excess amine. At an N/P ratio of 5, the polyplex formed by the cyclic grafted polymer with the highest DP of the pDMAEMA side chains exhibited the highest luciferase activity of all the reference polymers, and was 3.5 times more efficient at transfecting cells than the polyplex formed by its linear

analog. This polyplex also exhibited the highest percentage of transfected cells in *in vitro* studies and higher luciferase expression in mice.

Conclusions and outlook

This review examines the current state of the art in the synthesis of cyclic grafted polymers, highlighting key strategies and structural features and their potential biomedical applications. Over the past two decades, significant research efforts have focused on developing efficient and versatile synthetic protocols for constructing cyclic grafted polymers with well-defined architectures and a wide variety of backbones and side chains. Ring closure and ring expansion polymerization techniques have been instrumental in cyclization processes, while a variety of “grafting-through”, “grafting-onto” and “grafting-from” techniques have been crucial for generating side chains of different composition and structure. A novel approach, termed the "monomer route," was incorporated into this review. Despite current progress, several challenges remain. For instance, the synthesis of cyclic dendron-based architectures is still underexplored, reflecting a current limitation and ongoing challenge in the broader field of precision polymer synthesis. It is hypothesized that the potential of cyclic grafted polymers has yet to be realized and that implementing synthetic strategies is necessary to generate scalable amounts through robust processes. Strategies that enable the formation of cyclic grafted structures in a single reaction step, such as "grafting-through" and the "monomer approach," are the most scalable. However, these approaches have a limited range of available polymers, and controlling the final structures remains a research topic. For this reason, "grafting-from" and "grafting-onto" strategies are more often chosen to generate cyclic grafted structures, despite the critical limitation of having to generate the cyclic backbone beforehand. This includes the low scalability of the ring-closure approach and

the need to remove noncyclic impurities in both, the ring-closure and REP approaches. Similar to the synthesis of linear grafted polymers, “grafting-from” allows for higher grafting density, but it provides less control over uniformity and a higher risk of structural defects. In contrast, “grafting-onto” offers greater control over polymer chain characteristics, but has limited grafting density due to steric effects.

The impressive performance of cyclic grafted polymers in drug delivery and gene transfection underscores their versatility and potential applications in biomedicine. Adjusting their structural parameters is essential for forming supramolecular assemblies. This often results in enhanced drug loading capacity and improved *in vitro* and *in vivo* release profiles compared to their linear counterparts. Their cyclic backbone and multivalent side chains facilitate enhanced circulation profiles, controlled drug release, and receptor-targeted cellular uptake. However, challenges such as structure-property correlation and *in vivo* safety have yet to be fully addressed. The synthetic challenges associated with such complex structures may be the main obstacle to clinical experimentation. Given its relatively simple and scalable production, proven biocompatibility, and nontoxicity, branched cyclic polyglycerol could be a suitable candidate for clinical trials. Nevertheless, research into their potential applications in biomedicine is still in its early stages.

Overall, cyclic grafted polymers offer a powerful adaptable platform, and continued interdisciplinary research will likely unlock new frontiers in therapeutic innovation.

Corresponding author

Fabienne Barroso-Bujans: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9591-5646>

Email: f.barroso@ehu.eus; Telephone: +34 943018803

Data availability

No primary research results have been included and no new data were generated or analyzed as part of this review.

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